

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

TRANS CASPIAN HIGHWAY AND GEORGIAN CHALLENGES OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract

The problems created by the Russia-Ukraine war put the world "out of breath" with the lifting of the Covid restrictions in front of a completely new reality. It is a fact that the struggle for the establishment of a new world order has begun, which is best achieved by economically stable and strong countries. It is they who create the main agenda of the world.

Despite the small size of the territory and the economy, due to its geographical location, Georgia has a real chance to "turn its geographical location into a geopolitical location" in the new rearrangement of the world. That is why today the most important issue for our country is to correctly "perform" this role. However, before performing, it is more important to accept the role.

Keywords: New Silk Road, East-West Corridor, Trans-Caspian Highway, Georgia's geopolitical role.

Today, Georgia is in the field of global interests due to its geographical location between the countries of Western and Central Asia. Historically, it performed this role and function thousands of years ago, connecting the greatest civilizations in different parts of Eurasia with the famous "Great Silk Road". In this way, trade began in BC. year in the second century. It was connected to Transcaucasia by the Caspian Sea, and from Georgia to Byzantium by the Black Sea. For centuries, the existence of the Silk Road between the countries of the East and the West contributed to the exchange of economic and cultural relations, development, and technical progress. Religious ideas and spiritual values were spreading.

An opportunity to actively involve Georgia in the Great Silk Road appeared when economic problems arose between the countries (China, Russia, Iran...) due to a series of political events. As a result, the main trade roads and traffic were blocked and stopped. Sometimes this involved a long period of time and therefore it was necessary to find an alternative way. It was during the emergence of such a geopolitical situation that Georgia became a participant of the Great Silk Road, although there were even centuries when the main trade routes bypassed the country.

From the second half of the 90s of the 20th century, the integration of the mineral-rich Caspian Sea and Central Asia into the world economic processes began actively. Initially, the regional highways of the Europe-Caucasus-Asia transport corridor were created. Oil (Nabukko - Baku-Tbilisi - Ceyhan) and gas (Shahdeniz - Armenia Caucasian) pipelines.

In the current processes, a decisive role was assigned to the Caucasian transport corridor (Eurasia corridor) of energy resources passing through the territory of Georgia. It is from this time that Georgia's involvement in the TRACECA project begins.

The mentioned corridor had great support from the West, especially from the USA. Based on the implementation of this goal, the "Georgian International Oil Corporation" (GIOC) was founded, whose main task

was the transportation of oil extracted in the Caspian region and partnership with the world's leading oil companies.

Today, at the international level, both from the political and economic point of view, quite serious assessments are made about the increase in the geopolitical importance of Georgia. The geo-economic role "assigned" due to geographical location can be replaced by a geo-political one.

Despite the small size of the territory, the population and the economy itself, the interest in Georgia is quite large precisely because it has an important role in the new geopolitical relations, the establishment of which is already on the agenda.

The new agenda was "dictated" to the world by the Russia-Ukraine war. It is clear that Europe will no longer depend on Russian energy resources. Accordingly, more consumption of Asian countries' resources is now becoming active, which will lead to a load on the transit corridor from Asia to Europe. With the created reality and the increased interest in Georgia, it is possible to become a geopolitical player.

At the international level, it is already being talked about that the new rearrangement of the world will first of all be manifested by the fact that the border of Asia and Europe will move from the Urals to Georgia.

Georgia is considered to be the country which, for a number of reasons, can strengthen the connection between Europe and Asia. There are a number of positive factors that make it easy to choose Georgia. This highway will not only be a temporary way out of the current situation. On the contrary, with its potential, Georgia can turn the temporary "relocation" of the Great Silk Road into a solid prospect. Its active role is due to a number of factors, about which quite experienced and professional international and world-level experts speak boldly. Among many factors, in our opinion, several main signs can be distinguished:

- Among the post-Soviet countries (after the Baltics), Georgia is the most democratic.

- It has liberal economic legislation for access to economic activities. Therefore, economic activity in this country is much more comfortable than elsewhere.

- The ban on importing wine into Russia led to integration into European and international Western markets.

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- Many European and American enterprises and firms came to Georgia to "do" business. Individuals came for the same purpose.

- A significant part of the population speaks English at some level.

- The structure of the state has always been Georgian, which coincided with the Western one, the issues were resolved considering the laws based on Roman traditions (R. Chlochrelidze).

The transit corridor passing through the territory of the country includes container shipping, gas pipelines, oil and electricity supply. In fact, these are the main levers, the possibility of implementation of which is directly related to Georgia, as a country running the highway.

The Russia-Ukraine war gave completely new opportunities and perspectives to Georgia as one of the important corridors connecting Europe and Asia.

Both in the distant past and today, the main vectors of supply, distribution and redistribution of economic resources have changed in the economic relations of the world. The new geopolitical situation has led to the blocking and suspension of the main trade routes mentioned above. The world "needed" a new co-participant of the Eurasian highway. The created situation gave Georgia a real chance to build the Trans-Caspian highway. The conversation about the "New Silk Road" began. The country once again has an opportunity to play an important role in the new structure of world distribution.

At the official level, business meetings and negotiations have already started in order to reconcile the wishes, goals and objectives of the participating countries of the new highway and to find a common language for their interests. The government of Georgia can play the role of an important negotiator with reasonable actions, which is currently the best opportunity, and its loss will be tragic for the country (R. Klochrelidze).

The transportation of Kazakh oil through the transit line coming from Asia (through Azerbaijan) has already been decided and is in the starting phase, Turkmenistan is involved in the project of expanding the

Southern Corridor with the Trans-Caspian gas pipeline, the project of expanding the gas pipeline going to Europe through Georgia is being considered by the official Ashgabat. A completely new big project is on the agenda - an electric transmission cable that will be laid on the bottom of the Black Sea and will connect the Caucasus region with Europe.

Obviously, the implementation of the Trans-Caspian highway and its maximum load are related to many international factors and global events. Solving these issues depends a lot on the will and role of Europe.

Against the background of world challenges, the country should be able to form its own independent policy, which will play a serious role for a positive future perspective.

The status of a geopolitical role player offers Georgia quite a lot of serious news and challenges from the economic and political point of view:

- In the banking, financial and transit systems, it is desirable to implement projects corresponding to modern requirements and international standards.

- More work and specific effective measures are needed to improve the security of the country, especially since 20% of the territory is occupied by Russia. (Unfortunately, it has become less of a priority lately...), which will seriously increase the volume of foreign investments.

- It is no less important to maintain the role of a strategically interesting and worthy partner and to arrange concrete, open relations with the West.

- The country should not be thought of as the only carrier of the transit line. He should become a reliable and intelligent player of international level.

The new reality is a serious challenge for the economy of Georgia and it can be said that it is a new test. The most important thing is for the country to prepare the correct political decision for this exam, and the population of the country is the most infallible guarantee that it will pass this exam well.

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